

ISSN No: 4532-1113

abstrajournals.com

BEULAH HEIGHTS
UNIVERSITY

ATLANTA USA

892 Berne St SE, Atlanta, GA 30316, United States

Abstra International Journal of Psychology and Humanities

Volume 13 Issue 3, August 2024

103

ROLES PLAYED BY AFRICAN UNION TO MANAGE ETHNIC IDENTITY CRISIS IN RWANDA

^[1]Benson Adodo Michael, ^[2]Prof. Eugene T. Aliegba & ^[3]Prof. Yahaya Abdullahi Adadu

^[1,2,3] Department of Political Science, Faculty of Social Sciences, Nasarawa State University Keffi, Nigeria

Abstract

This paper examines the role of African Union (AU) in managed ethnic identity crisis in Rwanda. Ethnic identity inter-alia constitutes much of the structural indexes upon which society is built and developed, ethnic identity has remained an indelible and binding tool of association, attachment to one ideological belief or shared sentiment to secure common interest in reaction to socio-economic forces. This study employs descriptive research design. Data were collected through questionnaires and interviews, and both qualitative and quantitative methods were used for analysis. The theoretical framework adopted for this analysis is Neoliberal Institutional Theory. The findings of the study revealed that the roots cause of the Rwanda's crisis is highly polarized political identity based social structure which had its roots in the country's colonial and pre-colonial experience. Post-colonial politics in Rwandan were characterized by zero sum contests for power, fought along polarized racial lines. It was recommended that Politicians in Rwanda should desist from do-or-die syndrome. Election is not all about winning, they should learn to loss. Government should re-integrate all persons displaced by the crises. This can be done by building or assist rebuilding their homes, business and means of livelihood through provision of funds that will aid them self-sustained, and loans, subsidies and other incentives. Finally, continental and regional level, the African Union (AU) and other regional bodies should be involved in the processes of socializing Rwanda leaders and the people on the need for transparency and accountability in governance, and the diversification of the Rwanda economy to reduce poverty and speed up the processes of development.

How to Cite this Paper:

Benson Adodo Michael, Eugene T. Aliegba & Yahaya Abdullahi Adadu (2024) Roles Played by African Union to Manage Ethnic Identity Crisis in Rwanda, *International Journal of Psychology and Humanities*, Vol. 13(3) pp.103

DOI:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15094602>

Corresponding Author

Benson Adodo Michael

Keywords

Roles, African Union, Management and Ethnic Identity Crisis

INTRODUCTION

Ethnic identity crises have been a persistent source of conflict in Africa, leading to devastating civil wars, violence, and political instability. One of the most catastrophic examples of such crises is the Rwandan Genocide of 1994, in which approximately 800,000 people, mostly ethnic Tutsis and moderate Hutus, were killed in just over 100 days (Mamdani, 2001). The genocide was the result of deep-seated ethnic tensions between the Hutu majority and Tutsi minority, exacerbated by colonial legacies and political manipulation. The African Union (AU), which evolved from the Organization of African Unity

(OAU) in 2002, has played a pivotal role in addressing the aftermath of the Rwandan Genocide and has since been central to managing ethnic identity crises across the continent.

Samuel Huntington in his seminal work: *The Clash of Civilizations and the Remaking of the World Order* (1996), argues that the post-cold war era may not signal the end of history as Francis Fukuyama may want us to believe; rather the international system will witness the emergence of new social forces that are basically identity driven. These identity-based forces will be at the heart of conflicts in the world, and will resonate more within national boundaries. In his words: "In this new world the most pervasive, important and dangerous conflicts will not be between social classes, rich and poor, or other economically defined groups, but between peoples belonging to different cultural identities. Tribal wars and ethnic conflicts will occur within civilizations" (Huntington, 1996)

Africa is a multi-complex cultural and heterogeneous state of colonial creation with multi-dimensional ethnic and religious groupings with pre-colonial, colonial and post-colonial history. The roles played by Group Classification and National Identity in crimes of Genocide in Rwanda, Armenia, Nazi Germany, Bosnia etc. Are obvious incidences of gross abuses of identity (Horowitz, 1985).

Historical narratives have been invaluable in recognizing the genocide's complexity and refuting the "ancient hatreds" explanations for genocide. Hitherto, many scholars writing in the historicist vein tend to believe that primarily genocide is caused by "constructed" nature of ethnicity which is essentially not of biological category but a social and historical relationship, constructed over time, which becomes mobilized by elites in order to cause genocide. (Althusser, 1970).

In Nazi Germany in July 1938, only a few months before *Kristallnacht*, the infamous "*J-stamp*" was introduced on ID cards and later on passports. The use of specially marked "*J-stamp*" ID cards by Nazi Germany preceded the yellow Star of David badges. In Norway, where yellow cloth badges were not introduced, the stamped ID card was used in the identification of more than 750 Jews deported to death camps in Poland (Samuel, 1961). By the end of the genocide about thirteen million people were killed in the Holocaust. Six million of them were Jewish, (of which one million are children, two million are women) and the others were targeted by the Nazis because they were Roma, political dissidents, or homosexuals (Horowitz, 1985).

In April 1992, the government and people of Yugoslav republic of Bosnia Herzegovina declared its independence from Yugoslavia, Bosnian Serb forces, with the backing of the Serb dominated Yugoslav army attacked and massacre over 100,000 Bosnian (Bosnian Muslim) and Croatian civilians. (about 80 percent of the Bosnian population). (History.com 2010).

Rwanda within a space of one hundred days, between mid-April and July 1994 about 800,000 to 1,000,000 Tutsis were gruesomely killed and murdered by the Hutus led Government and Hutus armed Militias. Ethnic classification in Rwanda instituted by the Belgian colonial government and retained after independence, was central in shaping, defining and perpetuating ethnically based genocide of the Tutsis. Once the 1994 genocide in Rwanda began, an ID card with the designation "Tutsi" spelled a death sentence at any roadblock (Huttenbach, 1994). No other factor was more significant in facilitating the speed and magnitude of the 100 days of mass killing in Rwanda like the introduced ethnic identification card system (Kuperman, 2001).

Most countries in the world do some sort of official classification of their population by groups using one or more of categories such as national origin, race, ethnicity or religion. Most commonly this information is gathered during a census or on birth certificates (Kuperman, 2001). Such classification schemes treat group difference in overly simplified ways treating group identity as an unchanging constant not subject to ongoing changes in society (Huttenbach, 1994). What classification on national ID cards does is take group classification schemes one step further - from the classification of populations as a whole (in aggregate) - to the classification of individual persons by group. The effect of policies which apply group classifications upon individuals is to make group identity more rigid and to make one form of societal affiliation excessively prominent (usually religion or ethnicity), highlighting that particular area of difference above others, such as regional or local identity, social class or others. In most pluralistic societies a particular person's highlighted identity and affiliations differ by context and the situation at the moment; whereas in a rigid or polarized society a single identity is being reinforced and articulated.

The Organization of African Unity's (OAU) role reflected the dramatic changes that were occurring across the continent. On the one hand, the organization was responding to these changes in an attempt to remain relevant; on the other, the Rwanda experience helped shape the approach of the OAU to conflict management and resolution. Significantly, its efforts began to address the root causes of the internal conflicts it was facing, and its methods of consultation, mediation, and the involvement of regional leaders became stronger and more sophisticated (Prunier, 1995). These characteristics were well demonstrated in its intercession in the Rwandan tragedy, and if its efforts failed to prevent disaster, it was not for want of effort. We know now that only serious threats of military intervention or economic retaliation by the international community could have prevented the genocide, which indeed the OAU pressed for without success (Nichols, 2011).

It is also noted that the different ways that people describe the Rwanda Genocide are present in the literature, especially in relation to the role played by international bodies, but there is an absence of the Role of the AU underpinning the understanding of Rwanda Genocide in as well as the factors responsible for these Genocide. Equally, there is the absence of the traditional, cultural and non-material understanding and causes of Rwanda Genocide within the literature. This research filled this gap. That is why this paper is to examines the roles played by the African Union in managing the ethnic identity crisis in Rwanda, with a focus on its peacekeeping efforts, its support for transitional justice and reconciliation, and its broader contributions to conflict prevention and security in the region. By exploring the AU's interventions in Rwanda, this paper aims to highlight the evolving approach of the African Union in addressing ethnic conflicts in Africa. Understanding the AU's role in Rwanda can provide valuable insights into how regional organizations can manage ethnic identity crises and promote lasting peace in divided societies.

Research Questions

- i. To what extent did ethnic identity degenerate into Rwanda genocide?
- ii. What are the measures adopted in the management and integration of ethnic identity in Rwanda?

Objectives of the Study

- i. To examine the measures put in place by the African Union in the management of ethnic identity crisis in Rwanda
- ii. To interrogate the ways and manner at which African Union impacted on ethnic identity crisis in Rwanda

Conceptual Clarifications

The Concept of Ethnicity

The term *ethnic* has Latin and Greek origins – *ethnicus* and *ethnikas* both meaning nation. *Ethos*, in Greek, means custom, disposition or trait. *Ethnikas* and *ethos* taken together therefore can mean a band of people (nation) living together who share and acknowledge common customs. The second part of the construct, *identity*, has Latin origins and is derived from the word *identitas*; the word is formed from *idem* meaning *same*. Thus, the term is used to express the notion of sameness, likeness, and oneness. More precisely, identity means “the sameness of a person or thing at all times in all circumstances; the condition or fact that a person or thing is itself and not something else” (Simpson & Weiner, 1989). Combining the definitions and interpretations of identity and ethnicity, it can be concluded that they mean, or at minimum imply, the sameness of a band or nation of people who share common customs, traditions, historical experiences, and in some instances geographical residence. At one level of interpretation the combined definition is sufficient to capture the manner in which the identity is generally conceptualized and used to understand ethnocultural influences on its formation and development (Hardin, 1995).

Ethnicity refers to a category of people who identify with each other based on shared cultural traits such as language, religion, traditions, customs, and ancestry. Unlike race, which is often perceived as based on physical characteristics, ethnicity is rooted in social, historical, and cultural factors that define a group's way of life. Ethnic groups often share a common geographic origin and history, which can bind them through collective memories, experiences, and identities (Kellas, 1991).

Ethnicity plays a critical role in how individuals and groups perceive themselves and others. It is often linked to concepts of national identity, but it remains distinct as it can transcend or cut across national borders. For example, Kurdish people share an ethnic identity but are spread across several nation-states like Turkey, Iraq, and Syria. Ethnic identity can be fluid, changing as a result of migration, intermarriage, or cultural integration, but it usually remains deeply tied to heritage and tradition (Kuperman, 2000).

According to Cornell and Hartmann (1998), ethnicity is a form of social organization through which group boundaries are drawn, and members of an ethnic group differentiate themselves from others by emphasizing shared symbols and meanings. Ethnicity can therefore be both ascribed, meaning assigned at birth based on one's lineage, and achieved, where individuals choose to adopt or emphasize their ethnic affiliation later in life.

Ethnic Identity

There is no universally acceptable definition of ethnic identity, as its definition varies.

The first oblique reference to ethnic identity can be found in the anthropological and sociological literature of the early 20th century, in reference to the field study of non-western cultures.

Ethnic Identity refers to an individual's sense of belonging to a specific ethnic group, encompassing the shared heritage, cultural practices, language, religion, and traditions that distinguish one group from another. This identity is often shaped by historical, social, and cultural experiences, and can play a significant role in personal and group identity formation. It includes both a subjective sense of identity—how one perceives their own ethnicity—and an objective dimension, which relates to external recognition by others. Ethnic identity is fluid and can evolve over time in response to various social influences, migration, or intergroup dynamics (Breton, 1990).

The process of ethnic identity development involves individuals exploring and understanding the significance of their ethnic background. It is tied to broader concepts like race, nationality, and culture but remains distinct in focusing primarily on shared ancestry and cultural traits. Social scientists often distinguish between ethnic identity and racial identity, the former being more about cultural markers and the latter more about physical characteristics.

According to Tajfel's Social Identity Theory, ethnic identity also involves an in-group versus out-group dynamic, where people derive part of their self-concept from membership in an ethnic group. This contributes to a sense of pride, solidarity, or collective consciousness within the group, while potentially fostering prejudice or biases towards those seen as belonging to out-groups (Tajfel & Turner, 1986).

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

The African Union has since developed its peacekeeping capabilities through the African Standby Force (ASF), a continental force designed to respond quickly to crises, including ethnic conflicts. While the ASF has faced challenges in terms of capacity and deployment, its creation reflects the AU's commitment to preventing another genocide-like crisis on the continent. The AU's experience in Rwanda also informed the creation of the African Peace and Security Architecture (APSA), which aims to strengthen the continent's ability to respond to conflicts through early warning systems, conflict mediation, and peacekeeping missions (Engel & Porto, 2010).

In Rwanda, the AU's security efforts have been aimed at maintaining peace and preventing the resurgence of ethnic violence. While the Rwandan government under President Paul Kagame has taken strong measures to promote national unity and prevent ethnic divisions from re-emerging, the AU has continued to support regional stability efforts, recognizing that ethnic conflicts can easily spill over into neighboring countries (Williams, 2011). The AU's broader peacekeeping missions, including those in the Democratic Republic of Congo (DRC) and Burundi, have been crucial in preventing regional instability that could undermine Rwanda's post-genocide recovery.

The role played throughout the last decade by the Organization of African Unity (OAU), now African Union (AU). From the moment of the RPF invasion in 1990 through the Arusha negotiations, the creation of UNAMIR, of Opération Turquoise, and the subsequent wars of central Africa and the Great Lakes Region, the OAU has been an active, vocal, and key actor (Hardin, 1995). Its consistent goal has been to resolve the series of conflicts with as much dispatch and as little violence as possible. As we know only too well, its initiatives in Rwanda were ultimately unsuccessful. But there are lessons to be learned from this decade of involvement, above all the OAU's need for the capacity and the resources to back up its diplomatic ventures (Nichols, 2011).

In the process, the OAU's role reflected the dramatic changes that were occurring across the continent. On the one hand, the organization was responding to these changes in an attempt to remain relevant; on the other, the Rwanda experience helped shape the approach of the OAU to conflict management and resolution. Significantly, its efforts began to address the root causes of the internal conflicts it was facing, and its methods of consultation, mediation, and the involvement of regional leaders became stronger and more sophisticated (Prunier, 1995). These characteristics were well demonstrated in its intercession in the Rwandan tragedy, and if its efforts failed to prevent disaster, it was not for want of effort. We know now that only serious threats of military intervention or economic retaliation by the international community could have prevented the genocide, which indeed the OAU pressed for without success (Nichols, 2011).

The powers of the Secretary-General are substantially circumscribed by the unwieldy decision-making process and the need to work in concert with the member states, especially with regards to the ultra-sensitive political process of conflict management and resolution (Prunier, 1995).

The OAU Charter is categorical about the sovereignty of member states and about non-interference in their internal affairs. Attempts to deal with disputes and conflicts between states are complicated by the need to work within these strict guidelines. During the founding of the organization in 1963, the Assembly established a Commission of Mediation, Conciliation, and Arbitration. Alas, it was stillborn and has never worked. "As is known, it is the only permanent institutional framework provided for in the OAU Charter for the settlement of conflicts (Hardin, 1995). However, it has remained dormant from the first day of its establishment because member states have shown a strong preference for political process of conflict resolution rather than for judicial means of settlement. (OAU Press and Information Series 1, 1992).

Since its establishment in 1963, the OAU did not have its own legal and institutional preventive mechanism against Genocide, the only instrument dealing with human rights in detail, the African Charter on Human and Peoples' Rights (hereinafter the African Charter) provides generally for the protection and promotion of human rights. It also provides for an investigative and monitoring organ and mechanism. It allows the responsible organ, the Commission deal with human rights issues by drawing inspiration from international human rights law and instruments (Hardin, 1995). It was hoped that this would to redress the deficiencies of the African Charter. However, due to the absence of an enforcement mechanism and the African Charter's "excessive emphasis on the security and sovereignty of states", even OAU's successor the AU is unable to use its mandate to the fullest limit of the African Charter. The enforcement organs, like the African Court on Human and Peoples' Rights (hereinafter the Court) and mechanisms like the legal framework that has been developed to fit with the AU's function have not fully come in to force (Hardin, 1995).

The African Charter provides for a reporting and investigation mechanism so as to enable the Commission to do its human rights work. But here, although Rwanda acceded to the African Charter in 1983 it only submitted two reports about the human rights situation in the country (Prunier, 1995).

Therefore, the Commission did not take any effective step to demand that the government to improve on its reporting. Given Rwanda's historical background, the Commission should have, at least, sent rapporteurs and a more active part played in

promoting respect for of human rights in Rwanda. However, due to financial, logistical constraints, lack of uniform guidelines, and absence of country similarly Rapporteurs and lack of enforcement mechanisms and other constraints the Commission could not, till now, put a concrete input in providing cure to prevent future atrocities in Rwanda (Prunier, 1995).

During the last 10 years the OAU has attempted to adapt to the changing socio-economic and political conditions of the African continent. The Rwandan crisis and its regional aftermath have been one of these new challenges, and it is useful to examine the role of the OAU in Rwanda within this wider context (Prunier, 1995).

According to (Stoddard, 2012) the political Neutrality of the international community in the Rwandan crisis implies that most of the world stood on the sidelines during the Rwandan genocide, hoping to avoid the loss of life and political entanglement. This aggravated the Rwandan crisis and gave rise to the genocide in Rwanda. In the events that took place after the genocide, many government officials in the community mourned over the loss of many and were surprised about the world's obliviousness to the situation that could have prevented the massacre from taking place (Scott 2004). The Rwandan genocide did not interest the outside. The outbreaks in Rwanda were seen as not of sufficient interest and value to prevention of the violence and were not interested to warrant the expense of resources and the risk to losing more casualties. The delay caused thousands of Rwandan lives to be lost and mentally and psychologically scarred millions of those who lived the story (Stadler, 2012).

The world did not act, at least not very fast, to save the Tutsis. UN representatives and commanders were there and they also had some peacekeepers on the ground but their efforts were minimal (Lichback, and Zuckerman, 1997). "Western" countries or more developed countries did not act either. Even though most countries ratified the UN Convention on the Prevention and Punishment of the Crime of Genocide, nothing was done to stop the on-going on slaughter. There are several reasons nothing was done. The first is that this might have been a civil war and foreign states should not intervene in national self-determinations. Another explanation is that no one knew about the massacres that were occurring (Longman, 2011).

Could the UN have done anything to stop the on-slaughter? It is easy to blame the UN for their failure in stopping the violence, especially seeing emotional movies such as Hotel Rwanda or listening to testimonies recounting the horrors (Lawson, 1999). However, it is important to understand the UN was, especially at the beginning, unaware of the atrocities happening. Once knowledge that ethnic cleansing was occurring, the UN had to continue its primary purpose of establishing a cease-fire as well as keeping itself neutral in the conflict (Omaar, and De1995). Immediate action on the ground was difficult as the personnel had to follow UN procedures, and the UN Security Council was indeed trying to stay informed. However, "not enough accurate analysis was available to the Council" and thus it failed "to recognize the systematic and one-sided nature of the ethnic massacres until a few weeks later when more numerous reports, relating death totals of much great magnitude, became available." (Mitchelle, 2010). With poor information reaching the Security Council, and nothing that could be done on the ground, it is not surprising that nothing was done to stop the atrocities. Critics point out that UN personnel were at killing sites, not doing anything. They also mention that the UN could have taken out the Radio and Télévision Libre des Mille Collines, the national radio which was instigating the killings. However, as mentioned

earlier, killing violence instigators or disabling the radio would have put the UN in the middle of the political problem (Prunier, 1995). This would have been seen as giving an edge to the RPF, and would have taken the UN's neutrality away (Kellas, 1991). Even with reports on the grounds, the UN cannot act as decisively as a sovereign state, because of the bureaucracy involved in situations. It is also important to remember that the UN does not have a standing army, and thus would have needed to assemble a force comprised of multi-nationalities which most likely would have taken several months to create; and by that time the damage would have been done; the atrocities would be over (Hardin, 1995).

There was a UN document that showed that the UN's commander on the ground in Rwanda, General Romeo Dallaire, had an informant that gave the UN information of the atrocities that were going to happen. A fax sent to the UN headquarters in January of 1994 (a few months before the actual killings began) gave indications that executions were going to happen: "In 20 minutes [his Hutu militia] could kill up to 1,000 Tutsis." (Mitchelle, 2010).

This is overwhelming evidence that the UN knew something more was going to happen, or was it? This information was from a single source (Hardin, 1995). The UN had to make a decision on how credible this source was and how to act afterwards. Although there is no information on the credibility of the source (it is assumed he was credible because the facts given occurred later on that year), it is still important to realize that the United Nations could not do too much differently. There is no denying that this document was concerning, however it is unrealistic to assume that at the time the UN could have been able to act. In all probability, placing more troops in Rwanda would not have changed much since the UN had to stay neutral and would need to continue working on reaching a cease-fire (Johnson, 2010).

Theoretical Framework (Neoliberal Institutional Theory)

This paper is anchor on the neoliberal institutionalist theory as proposed by Keohane (1984) and Snyder (1999). The theorists believe that states are or at least should be concerned, first and foremost, with absolute gains rather than relative gains as they relate with other states. This theory argues that for there to be peace in the international affairs, states must cooperate together and in effect yield some of their sovereignty to create integrated communities to promote economic growth and respond to continental and international security issues. This clearly shows that for states like Nigeria and her immediate neighbours; matters of common security should be considered an absolute gain that all the states within the sub-region should be concerned especially that their borders are very fluid that insecurity in one state could mean insecurity in the other (Usman & Mustapha, 2017).

This theory often employs game theory to explain why states do or do not cooperate (Keohane, 1984). Since this approach tends to emphasize the possibility of mutual wins, they are interested in institutions (the AU for instance) which can arrange joint profitable arrangements and compromise. The neo liberalist argued that even in an anarchical system of autonomous rational states, cooperation can emerge through the cultivation of mutual trust and building of norms, regimes and institutions.

Also, states' internal and domestic limitations are important aspects of continental security cooperation development. As Etel Solingen emphasizes, the form or nature of a state's governance is an essential explanatory factor influencing security policy, assuming that "the democratic nature of states is a fundamental piece of the puzzle in understanding

conflict and cooperation Solingen further hypothesizes that political coalitions favouring liberal domestic reform policies will engage in continental cooperation, if they view a strong commitment in their partners. By contrast, Steven R. David argues that leaders in developing countries are often caught in the balance between internal threats and external ones while considering alliance formation, which explains the sometimes-anomalous alliances these states form with external actors. Jentleson and Kaye argue that “continental actors” would need “leadership survival concerns, coalitions types or other political and economic constraints within the state” to motivate them to “engage” and then to refrain from continental cooperation. This debate on domestic-based influence certainly explains state behaviour toward continental security cooperation.

Snyder’s arguments threw up the issue of collective Security as applied by the league of Nation when it was founded in 1917. Neoliberal institutionalisms argued that collective security can facilitate the transformation of the competitive nature of state relations into a peaceful system of demilitarized interstate competition, based on the rule of law. Neoliberal institutionalisms further argued that a collective security system can facilitate such a process by changing the interests and behavior of states, as they become more aware of shared interests and security concerns. The theory draws inspiration from both the realist and idealist theories and most particularly the Balance of power principle. The theory favors the UN argument of collective security basing its central premise on the statement that an attack on one state, is an attack on all states in the particular system; and that all states have to stop the aggressor (Snyder, 1999).

Analysts of the status-identity approach argue that the enhancement of a state’s security through continental cooperation might also influence negatively its relative standing in other ways. From a constructivist point of view, though, how a state sees itself in the world can influence its interests and involvement in continental security cooperation. As a result, concerns related to identity-based status can impact negatively on cooperation processes, despite the incentives for cooperative arrangements offered by strategies or domestic conditions. Therefore, continental security cooperation comes with advantages as well as possible disadvantages. These overall theoretical paradigms presented by Jentleson and Kaye contribute to the debates regarding various aspects of continental security cooperation, ranging from the threat environment to internal issues and down to nonmaterial characteristics.

Regardless of how cooperation is defined or interpreted, the conclusions indicate differences regarding how to achieve effectiveness in continental security cooperation in managing internal crisis. While some scholars agree that continental security cooperation presents many challenges that alter its effectiveness, other scholars claim that continental security cooperation is a valuable way to deal with security issues when member states perceive a threat at similar levels. Additional perspectives view and evaluate continental security cooperation under a broader and more comprehensive approach in terms of geographic proximity and the mobilization of member states’ elements of national power. One school of thought views continental security cooperation as a single effective aspect to tackle a collective threat, whereas an opposing point of view sees it working well while as a collective effort. For example, Eric Rosand, Alistair Millar, and Jason Ipe observe that the Intergovernmental Authority on Development (IGAD) initially focused on development “but gradually took on security functions, underscoring the reality of the intimate relationship between security and development in the horn of Africa.” The organization has made

tremendous progress through capacity building including legislation and training in fighting terrorism in the continent. Therefore, various supportive and opposing arguments surround the concept of continental security cooperation.

Transnational terrorism is diverse and multifaceted regarding scope and intensity. Dealing with it requires investment in international security and diplomacy. It also entails cooperation between domestic, regional and international actors in the areas of peace, security and development. More so, contemporary terrorism has deviated from the traditional choice of targeting military establishments and governments to targeting vulnerable civilian population. Buzan also includes three levels of analysis: individual, state and the international system. For the theorists, national security depends on the dynamics of international relations (especially regional ones), but a parallel should not be made between national and international security (Buzan & Waeber, 1998).

In Africa, more extensive forms of regional security cooperation are pursued but currently faces wide spread domestic political instability, which can spread across borders through flows of refugee, armed rebels and other potential conduit of disruption.

Relevance of the Theory to the Study

The theory is very relevant to this study since it is not predicated on the notion of each for his own, but on a notion of all for one; one for all. Moreover, the contribution of troops in this kind of arrangement will help Nigeria as a state augment some of its weaknesses in strategic security.

The major Strength of the neoliberal institutionalisms theory is multilateral cooperation between states that shares common interest is vital in combating issues of security threat in Rwanda given the trans-border character of the organization. For neighboring or relatively close states that have very common problems it is considered a legal right (absolute gain) for them to cooperate on areas where they share common interest toward self-defense. Therefore, AU established against future and unknown threats like the one presented by the identity crisis in Rwanda can be understood in this context. It could be very useful to explain the collective threat that the AU is meant to deal with through collective efforts of the members in the force.

Nevertheless, the neoliberal institutionalist theory is weak in the explanation of the role unequal power relations and resources among states play in managing internal crisis, especially its efforts in Rwanda genocide. This clearly show that issues related to diverse capabilities of states that formed AU hamper efforts at combating crisis within a state in the continent.

METHODOLOGY

To achieve the proposed research questions, this study used a discriptive research design which entails both qualitative and quantitative approaches. The population of the study is 101 people comprising African Union, Rwanda Embassy and United Nations. The sample size of the study is 80 determined using Krejcie and Morgan (1970). In addition, responses from selected interviewees using purposive sampling technique were used to supplement result from questionnaire analysis.

Table 1: Table Showing the Population of the Study

Targeted stakeholders	Population	Percentage
African Union	42	41.58
Rwanda of Embassy	30	29.70
United Nations	29	28.71
TOTAL	101	100

Source: As compiled by the researcher, 2024.

DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION OF RESULTS

The data were analyzed using simple percentage technique. The process requires placing each sun of the number of questionnaires administered on the respondents against the total population.

Table 1: What is the main cause (s) of Rwanda genocide?

Response	No of responded	Percentage %
Political	53	66.25%
Religious	22	27.5%
Ethnicity	3	3.75%
All of the above	2	2.5%
Total	80	100

Source: Field Work 2024

Table 1 above shows that 66.35% of the respondents think the main cause of ethno-religious is political, 27.5% attributed the conflict to religious, 3.75% believe the conflict has ethnic undertone, while 2.5% believe that all of the above factors are responsible for the ethnic identities conflict. From the above, it is revealed that the main cause of the genocide crisis in Rwanda is not clear and could be attributed to political, religious and ethnic connotation.

In an interview on the possible cause of the Rwanda Genocide and the respondents at the Rwanda Embassy stated that:

The arrival of central authority lines of distinction were altered and sharpened as the categories of Hutu and Tutsi assume new hierarchical overtones associate with proximity to the central court. Proximity to power when the political arena widened and the intensity of political activities increased. This stratified and rigidified. As the Rwandan society was organized into racial hierarchies, the Tutsis, the superior group by definition, became the "natural candidates" for assisting colonizers. Considered as inferior, the Hutus were condemned to be "naturally dominated". The indirect colonial rule system, like a company director who recruits employees for his/her company branch, had no other option but to select the intermediaries among the elements who were "genetically the best".

Table 2: What ways do you think crisis can be managed in Rwanda?

Response	No of responded	Percentage %
Tolerance	45	56.25%
Enlightenment	14	17.5%
Qualitative Education	10	12.5%
All of the above	11	13.75%
Total	80	100

Source: Field Work 2024

Table 2 above shows that 56.25% of the respondents are of the view that Rwanda Crisis can be best manage through tolerance, 17.5% think conflict can be managed through proper enlightenment, 12.5% suggested that ethnic identity conflict can be managed through qualitative education, while 13.75% believe that all of the above factors can be the solution to curtail ethno-religious crisis in Rwanda. From the above, it is revealed that tolerance is the only antidote and best way of managing ethnic identity and Rwanda crisis.

In an interview on the possible cause of the Rwanda Genocide and the respondents at the Rwanda Embassy stated that:

The African Union initiated vital steps towards the creation of a peace and security council (PSC) which serves as the decision making institution and the sole authority for deploying, managing and terminating AU-led peace operations .The rationale for its establishment came through mutual concern expressed by the Heads of State and Government and member states of the AU about the "Continued Prevalence of armed conflicts in Africa and the fact that no single internal factor has contributed more to socio-economic decline on the continent and the suffering of the civilian population than the scourge of conflicts within and between states"³ . The reason for its establishment was found in a firm awareness that the development of strong democratic institutions, and the observance of human rights and the rule of law, as well as the implementation of post-conflict recovery programmes are essential for the promotion of collective security, durable peace and stability as well as for the prevention of conflicts.

The use of the ethnic phenomenon in political affairs by the colonizer has resulted in some factors which are sometimes closely related ideological beliefs, the principle of indirect colonization which is likely to rely on competent and favourable natives, segregation in schools, the principle of "divide and rule" and the decolonization.

CONCLUSION

The African Union's role in managing the ethnic identity crisis in Rwanda demonstrates its evolving approach to conflict management and peacebuilding on the continent. From the failure of the OAU during the genocide to the AU's more proactive stance in post-genocide Rwanda, the organization has learned valuable lessons about the importance of regional cooperation, peacekeeping, and justice in addressing ethnic conflicts. In Rwanda, the AU has played a critical role in supporting peacebuilding efforts, promoting justice and reconciliation, and preventing the recurrence of ethnic violence. These efforts have not only contributed to Rwanda's recovery but have also informed the AU's broader strategy for managing ethnic identity crises across Africa.

The experience in Rwanda highlights the need for regional organizations like the AU to develop comprehensive strategies for preventing and managing ethnic conflicts. The AU's involvement in Rwanda reflects its commitment to ensuring that such crises do not lead to further violence and instability, not only in Rwanda but across the continent. As the African Union continues to strengthen its peace and security mechanisms, Rwanda's recovery from

the 1994 genocide will serve as a critical reference point for future interventions in ethnically divided societies.

Recommendations

The recommendations are as follows:

- i. Politicians in Rwanda should desist from do-or-die syndrome. Election is not all about winning, they should learn to lose. Thus, rigging election should be stopped, religious and ethnic leaders on the hand should be insulated from politics and rather serve as custodian of peace and “father to all” instead of taking side. The land tenure system in Rwanda should be overhauled. This issue of “settle-indigene” dichotomy need to be set aside, provided the land is secured, nobody should have the right to send a fellow Rwanda indigene out of the particular place or community. This can be achieved by preaching love, tolerance, mutual trust and affection.
- ii. Government should re-integrate all persons displaced by the crises. This can be done by building or assist rebuilding their homes, business and means of livelihood through provision of funds that will aid them self-sustained, and loans, subsidies and other incentives should be given to farmers so as to embark on large scale farming which will take the country away from food insecurity to food sufficiency.

Finally, continental and regional level, the African Union (AU) and other regional bodies should be involved in the processes of socializing Rwanda leaders and the people on the need for transparency and accountability in governance, and the diversification of the Rwanda economy to reduce poverty and speed up the processes of development. Moreover, not waiting for the outbreak of violence, and then, involved in peacekeeping operations.

References

- Althusser, L. (1970) For Marx. Ben Brewster, Trans. New York: Vintage Books.
- Clark, P. (2010). The gacaca courts, post-genocide justice and reconciliation in Rwanda: justice without lawyers. Cambridge University Press.
- Cornell, S., & Hartmann, D. (1998). Ethnicity and race: making identities in a changing world. thousand oaks, ca: pine forge press.
- Des Forges, A. (1999). Leave none to tell the story: genocide in Rwanda. human rights watch.
- Diamond, and Plattner (1994). Rwanda and genocide in the twentieth century: published in 1995 by plato press, 345 archway road, london n6 5aa
- Engel, U., & Porto, J. G. (2010). Africa’s new peace and security architecture: promoting norms, institutionalizing solutions. ashgate publishing.
- Hardin, R., (1995) One for all: the logic behind group conflict, princeton, new jersey: princeton university press.
- History of Rwanda. EconomicExpert.com, 25 April 2010. Web. 25 April 2010. History.com:
- Johnson, B (2010). Why is there conflict between Tutsis and Hutus? About.com, Web. 25 April 2010.
- Jones, B. (2001). Peacemaking in Rwanda: the dynamics of failure. Lynne Rienner Publishers.

- Kellas, J. G., (1991). *The politics of nationalism and ethnicity*, london, uk: mac millan education ltd.
- Kuperman, A. J. (2001). *The limits of humanitarian intervention; genocide in rwanda*: brookings institute press, 1775 massachusetts avenue, nw; washington dc 20036.
- Longman, T (2011). "Identity cards, ethnic self-perception, and genocide in rwanda," in caplan, jane and torpey, john c. *documenting individual identity: the development of state practices in the modern world*. (princeton university press, united states of america.
- Mamdani, M (2001) *When Victims Become Killers: colonialism, Nativism, and the Genocide in Rwanda*. Princeton University Press.
- Mitchelle. (2010) *False History: Real Genocide: The Use and Abuse of Identity in Rwanda*. Change.org, Web. 25 April 2010.
- Nichols, 2011
- OAU Press and Information Series 1, 1992).
- Omaar, R. and De W., Alex, (1995) *Rwanda: Death, Despair and Defiance*, London, UK: African Rights,.
- Prunier, G. 1995. *The Rwanda Crisis: History of a Genocide*. New York: Columbia University Press.
- Simpson & Weiner, 1989
- Stadler, 2012
- Stoddard, A. (2009). "Ethno nationalism and the Failed State: Sources of Civil State Fragmentation in the International Political Economy." *E-Merge: A Graduate Journal of International Affairs* 3(2002): 4-5. 05 April 2009,
- Tajfel, H., & Turner, J. C. (1986). The social identity theory of intergroup behavior. In S. Worchel & W. G. Austin (Eds.), *Psychology of Intergroup Relations* (pp. 7-24). Chicago: Nelson-Hall.
- Williams, P. D. (2011). *War & Conflict in Africa*. Polity Press.